

Determinant of Carbon Emissions Disclosure Among Listed Firms in Nigeria

Rowland Osamudiname Ogbebor

Department of Accounting, Sports University of Nigeria (SUN), Idumuje Ugboko, Nigeria
Email: rowlandogbebor143@gmail.com

Comfort Ibhalkholor Iserameiya

Department of Accounting, Ambrose Ali University, Ekpoma, Nigeria
Email: barrcomfort46@gmail.com

Jude Ikponmwonsa Ogbebor

Department of Economics, University of Benin, Nigeria
Email: judeogbebor10@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study investigates the determinants of carbon emission disclosure by drawing samples from listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022. In this study, firm size profitability proxied by return on asset, and ownership concentration are the determinants criteria explored in this study in line with related extant literature. The population of the study consists of all the listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022. As of December 2022, we had 9 oil and gas firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group. The sampling technique employed in this study is the filtering sampling technique since firms will be included in the sample on certain selection criteria. The final sample size will consist of 7 listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Overall, the empirical findings of this study are mixed in proving the criteria influencing the disclosure of carbon emission reporting by drawing samples from listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that a 1% increase in firm size will significantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 18% during the period under study. Furthermore, the study concludes that a 1% increase in profitability will significantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 9% during the period under study. The result implies that a 1% increase in ownership concentration will insignificantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 1% during the period under study. In general, this study recommends that large firms should try to report more on carbon emission to bridge information asymmetry and increase stakeholders' confidence. Furthermore, there is a tendency to maintain the informative asymmetry and correspondingly potentially higher conflicts of interest, to the detriment of other stakeholders, particularly minority shareholders, assuming a strict link between the majority shareholders and the board of directors.

1 Introduction

Carbon emission disclosure is a form of contribution of entities to environmental changes, especially global warming. The existence of a business entity certainly cannot be separated from the community environment where the activities of the company are required to be in harmony with the values and norms prevailing in the community. This causes an increase in the company's information needs related to the disclosure of the environment, especially carbon emission disclosure due to the demands. Therefore, companies should increase carbon emission disclosure to gain legitimacy from the environment. There are many factors affecting carbon emission disclosure. Choi et al. (2023) mentions influential factors that are industry type, carbon emission level, company size, and corporate governance quality. Ghomi and Leung (2023) find that company size, company's age, and institutional ownership structure affect carbon emission disclosure. Jannah and Muid (2014) state that exposure media, industry type, profitability, company size, and leverage have an effect on carbon emission disclosure. Based on the previous studies, researchers conduct further testing related to factors that affect carbon emission disclosure in Indonesian companies. Disclosure of carbon emission is a form of company's contribution to environmental changes, especially global warming.

Disclosure of carbon emission is usually reported in annual reports and / or sustainability reports. Theories that explain the disclosure of carbon emission in this study are legitimacy theory, stakeholder theory, and agency theory. Legitimacy theory describes companies and societies having social contracts in which companies have a demand to align corporate activities with values and norms prevailing in the community so that the companies get the legitimacy (recognition) from the community. Stakeholder theory explains that the company in running the company not only to seek profit but also provide benefits to stakeholders. Agency theory explains that there is information asymmetry between agents (Management) and principals (shareholders). Companies with superior environmental performance have a proactive environmental strategy (Clarkson et al., 2018). The theory of legitimacy explains that the company has a social contract with the community. The company is expected to perform its activities in accordance with the values and norms prevailing in the community so that the company gets recognition from the public. This can be obtained by aligning the company's activities with the values and norms of society such as by preserving the surrounding environment. The better the environmental performance the higher the company is to gain legitimacy from the community.

Most countries are concerned about global warming and are trying to find ways to reduce greenhouse gases to overcome climate change (Rokhmawati *et al.*, 2017); (Egbunike and Emudainohwo, 2017). Paris climate accord, concluded in 2016, reflects on this concern (Yu & Lee, 2017). Carbon emission disclosure is a part of an entity's contribution to environmental and climate changes, particularly on global warming. Global warming phenomenon has now become an increasingly important issue in most countries (Liu et al., 2015); (Asmeri et al., 2017). The appeal for companies to mitigate climate change challenges can also be justified. An important aspect of climate change mitigation is the company's obligation to recognize, measure, record, present and disclose their carbon emissions (Kalu et al., 2016); (Rokhmawati and Gunardi, 2017). The study Kalu et al. (2016) also suggested that carbon disclosure acts as a means of achieving public trust and legitimacy. Previous research has examined the disclosure of carbon emissions from various aspects, both in Nigeria and abroad.

The initial motivation for this study was created by the decision to investigate carbon emission disclosures in Nigeria, an emerging economy, because prior research has generally focused on the carbon emission disclosure practices of developed countries (Rankin et al., 2011; Choi et al., 2013; Liao et al., 2015; Yunus et al., 2016; Ben-Amar et al., 2017). Previous empirical studies have mainly explored the link between GHG emission disclosures and conventional company characteristics, such as firm size, profitability, leverage, firm age and industry (Prado-Lorenzo et al., 2009; Chithambo and Tauringana, 2014; Gonzalez-Gonzalez and Ramirez, 2016). On the other hand, very few studies have investigated the impact of specific firm attributes (e.g. ownership structure) on corporate reporting practices relative to carbon emissions (Liao et al., 2015; Yunus et al., 2016; Ben-Amar et al., 2017). Hence, this study examines the determinants of carbon emission reporting of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

2 Literature and Hypothesis Development

Carbon emission can be defined as gases containing carbon emitted to the Earth's atmospheric layers which are commonly derived from combustion process. The Ministry of Environment and Forestry (2018) classifies the gases into CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, HFCs, C₄F₉OC₂H₅, CHF₂OCF₂OC₂F₄OCHF₂, and so on. Carbon emission or greenhouse gas may be divided by source into two, namely natural greenhouse gas and industrial greenhouse gas. The industrial and energy sectors are human activities that produce abundant carbon dioxide. The industrial sector's use of energy from fossil derived fuel such as oil and coal has caused an increasing amount of greenhouse gas in the Earth's atmosphere (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2018). Carbon emission disclosure is a type of environmental disclosure. The intensity of GHG emission or greenhouse gas and use of energy, corporate governance and strategy related to the impacts of climate change are covered in environmental disclosure (Cotter *et al.*, 2011). Companies are demanded to be more open regarding information about any activities they do and their form of accountability. The openness of information about a company's activities and its accountability is a demand on a company. Information disclosure in annual reports is a form of a company's transparency and accountability. The information disclosure in annual report consists of two groups, namely mandatory disclosure and voluntary disclosure (Darrough, 1993).

In the view of Kumar, Pranitha, and Kumar (2017), green accounting measure records and disclose the effect of corporate environmental actions on its financial standing using a set of accounting systems. Environmental accounting aims to enable companies to achieve sustainable development and pursue efficient and effective environmental conservation activities while maintaining a good relationship with the company's community. This process aids organizations in identifying the cost of engaging in environmental conservation activities, the benefits gained from conservation activities provided in quantifiable means of measurement and support the communication of the evaluation results carried out to the stakeholders. Environmental accounting is a subset of accounting that incorporates economic and ecological information conducted on a corporate or national level. Environmental accounting has three sub-discipline categories: Global, national, and corporate environmental accounting. Global environmental accounting deals with energetics, ecology, and economics on a global level. National environmental accounting deals with economics, energetics, and ecology on a national (country) level (Adegbie 2020).

Firm size has to do with how large or small a company is in terms of assets, branch network (Shadrach & Yakura, 2021). Firm size is one of the characteristics of firms that differ in many

ways, and it is important in considering how the size generates quality information. Firm size deals with the number of resources owned by a firm or company. The size of a company or firm can be represented by total assets, number of sales, average sales, and average total assets. Asset size is considered as the most appropriate means by which firms are measured. Atu (2016); Suwito and Herawaty (2015) define the size of a company as a large-scale in which small ones can be classified according to a variety of ways. This includes total assets, market value of shares, and others. They revealed that bigger companies engage greatly in income smoothing or creative accounting than smaller companies. This is done because of the greater political cost associated with bigger companies.

A bigger company is likely to manage earnings by decreasing its revenue. Firm size motivates voluntary disclosure practices due to regulations such as tax regulations, banking regulations, etc. Political costs erupt due to the high possibility of the company performance being by the media and consumers. Larger attention from analysts and more recognizable than the smaller firms. This is as a result of concerns such as the high profit fluctuations that will attract attention and deliver unexpected impact (Ashiq, Guoxing, Tabassam & Waheed, 2022). In this case, managers increase their companies' earnings by manipulating achieved results to avoid negative impacts that may occur and to maintain the company's reputation. Thus, another reason for the negative effect between firm size and voluntary disclosure is the reputation cost. In large firms the reputation cost is higher than that in the small firms as large firms have better appreciation of market environment, better control over their operations and better understanding of their businesses relative to small-sized firms, therefore this might prevent large firms from engaging in voluntary disclosure practices. Thus, we state the following hypotheses:

H1: Firm size is not a significant determinants of carbon emission reporting among listed firms in Nigeria

Profit is the primary objective of a business (Nimalathan, 2009). Profit in the accounting sense tends to become a long-term objective which measures not only the success of the product, but also of the development of the market for it. It is determined by matching revenue against cost associated with it. Only those costs are placed against revenue, which have a contribution in the generation of such revenue. An enterprise should earn profits to survive and grow over a long period of time. It provides evidence concerning the earnings potential of a company and how effectively a firm is being managed. If the enterprise fails to make profit. Capital invested is eroded and if this situation prolongs the enterprise ultimately ceases to exist. Profit and profitability are two different terms. Profit is an absolute measure of earning capacity, while profitability is a relative measure of earning capacity.

Profit is defined by Iyer (1995) as "excess of return over outlay" (Nimalathan, 2009) while profitability is defined as "the ability of a given investment to earn a return from its use". The word profitability is composed of two words: profit and ability. The word profit has already been defined but the meaning of profit differs according to the use and purpose of the enterprise to earn the profits. Thus, the word profitability may be defined as the ability of a given investment to earn a return from its use. Profitability ratios measure the firm's ability to generate profits and central investment to security analysis, shareholders, and investors. Profitability is the primary measure of the overall success of an enterprise. The analysis of profitability ratios is important for the

Shareholders, creditors, prospective investors, bankers, and government alike. Profitability is defined as return on investment and is measured by the net income to total shareholder's equity for the period. Profitability or Performance (ROE) is used as a proxy of quality of management II hypothesis. Thus, we state the following hypotheses:

H2: Profitability is not a significant determinants of carbon emission reporting among listed firms in Nigeria

Ownership concentration, defined by Demsetz & Lehn (1985) as the extent to which a small number of shareholders control a significant portion of a company's shares, plays a crucial role in shaping corporate governance and decision-making. This concept has been further explored by scholars such as Khalil, Syed, & Zahid (2022), who emphasize that concentrated ownership often results in these shareholders wielding substantial influence over a company's strategic directions, including its approach to environmental practices like carbon emission reporting. In firms with high ownership concentration, major shareholders may prioritize sustainability and transparency as a means of protecting their long-term investments. For example, Demsetz & Villalonga (2021) argue that when ownership is concentrated among shareholders with a long-term perspective, such as institutional investors or family owners, these shareholders may advocate for detailed carbon emission reporting to mitigate risks associated with environmental liabilities and enhance the firm's reputation. This aligns with the view of Chiara (1997), who suggests that concentrated ownership can lead to greater focus on productivity and sustainable practices, driven by the interests of large institutional owners.

Conversely, ownership concentration can also lead to a short-term focus, particularly if the dominant shareholders are primarily interested in maximizing immediate financial returns. As noted by Demsetz & Lehn (1985), when concentrated owners prioritize short-term gains, they might resist comprehensive carbon emission reporting, viewing it as an additional cost that could detract from profitability. Similarly, Ram & Camela (2022) highlight that in such scenarios, the strategic decisions made by these shareholders might downplay the importance of environmental transparency, favoring actions that boost short-term financial performance instead. The dual potential impact of ownership concentration—either promoting or hindering carbon emission reporting—depends largely on the specific objectives and time horizons of the controlling shareholders. This complexity is further illustrated by Alipour & Amjadi (2021), who describe how the composition of ownership, including the presence of institutional, individual, and managerial shareholders, can influence the degree to which environmental reporting is prioritized within a firm. Thus, we state the following hypotheses:

H3: Ownership concentration is not a significant determinants of carbon emission reporting among listed firms in Nigeria

3 Research Design and Data

In this study, the *ex-post facto* research design is employed. Furthermore, to answer the research questions, the *ex-post facto* research design allows us to retrieve the needed data from the annual report of oil and gas firms from 2013 to 2022. The population of the study consists of all the listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022. As of December 2022, we had 9 oil and gas firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) (NGX Factbook, 2022). The sampling

technique employed in this study is the filtering sampling technique since firms will be included in the sample on certain selection criteria. These criteria include that the firms are listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group market for the period between 2013-2022; there was access to their annual financial reports within the period and they were not firms operating subsidiaries in Nigeria that are not listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group Market. Furthermore, newly listed firms are also excluded from the study. Summarily, only oil and gas firms that had all relevant data due to continuous existence within the study period were included in the sample. The final sample size will consist of 7 listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The econometric form of the study’s model is expressed as follows:

$$\ln\left(\frac{CAEM}{1 - CAEM}\right)_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FSIZ_{it} + \beta_2 PROF_{it} + \beta_3 OWNC_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

- CAEM = Carbon Emission Disclosure
- FSIZ = Firm size
- PROF = Profitability
- OWNC = Ownership Concentration
- β_0 = Constant
- $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Slope Coefficient
- μ = Stochastic disturbance
- i = i^{th} company
- t = time period

This study employs analytical software of Stata version 16 and Microsoft excel for the analysis. The secondary data collected is analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis. The descriptive statistics will be used to evaluate the characteristics of the data: mean maximum, minimum, and standard deviation and also check for normality of the data. Logistic regression will be employed to test the hypotheses of this study. Particularly, logistic regression is use in this study based on the following reasons. First, logistic regression has the advantage of being less affected than discriminant analysis when the basic assumptions particularly normality of the variables, are not met (Hair Jr, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & Kuppelwieser, 2014). Second, in logistic regression, the estimated coefficients can be interpreted separately as the significance of each of the predictive variables. Third, statistically, logistic regression seems to fit well with the features of the carbon reporting prediction problem, where the dependent variable is binary and with the groups being discrete, non-overlapping and identifiable (Ciampi 2015). Fourth, it has straightforward statistical tests, similar approaches to incorporating metric and non-metric variables and non-linear effects, and a wide range of diagnostics (Hair Jr et al. 2014). Fifth, logistic regression produces reliable results because of its ability to produce a nonlinear transformation of the input data that reduces the effects of outliers.

S/N	Variables	Measurements	Sources	Apriori Sign
Dependent Variable				
1	Carbon Emission Reporting	Carbon emission reporting is measured as “1” where companies disclose information relating to greenhouse gasses and “0” for otherwise.	Leal, Rodrigues, Lima de Freitas, and Lagioia (2019)	
Independent Variables				
1	Firm size	Firm size is computed as the natural logarithm of Total asset	Samak, El Said and El Latif (2014)	+ -
2	Profitability	Profitability is measured in terms of return on assets. Return on asset in percentage is computed as profit after tax divided Total asset	Samak, El Said and El Latif (2014)	+ -
3	Ownership Concentration	Ownership concentration in percentage is the shares ownership concentration of all the block shareholders with 5% and above controlling interest.	Ahmad & Kamarudin, (2003)	+ -

Source: *Author’s Compilation (2025)*

4 Results and Discussion

The study investigates the determinants of carbon emission disclosure by drawing samples from listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022. In this study, firm size (FSIZ) profitability (PROF) proxied by return on asset, and ownership concentration (OWNC) are the determinants criteria explored in this study in line with related extant literature. Particularly, this chapter shows the descriptive statistics, normality of data test, correlation analysis, regression analysis, test of hypotheses, and the discussion of findings. In testing for the determinants of carbon emission disclosure among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria, the study conducted a binary logistics regression in addition to correlation analysis. However, the study also performs preliminary pre-regression analysis such as descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and normality test, the results are analysed as follows.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis

In this section, the study examines the descriptive statistics for both the explanatory and dependent variables of interest. Each variable is examined based on the mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum. Table 1 below displays the descriptive statistics for the study.

Table 4.1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
caem	70	.143	.243	0	1
fsiz	70	7.929	.479	7.120	9.060
prof	70	1.295	.428	-71.360	176.270
ownc	70	53.671	13.345	6	89

Source: Author (2025)

The table above shows the descriptive statistics of the study. The table shows that the mean of the dependent variable of carbon emission disclosure (CAEM) was 0.143 with a standard deviation of 0.243 indicating that on average, about 14% of the oil and gas firms in Nigeria disclosed information related to carbon emission during the period under study. In the case of the determinants variables, the study shows that the mean of firm size (FSIZ) was 7.929 with a standard deviation of 0.479. The mean of profitability as measured in terms of return on asset (PROF) was 1.295 with a standard deviation of 0.428. Finally, the mean of ownership concentration (OWNC) was 53.671 with a standard deviation of 13.345 indicating that on average, about 54% of the shareholding of the firms under study were concentrated during the period under study.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

In this study, the Spearman rank correlation is employed since the data employed does not come from a normal distribution. The result obtain from the Spearman correlation is presented.

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
(1) caem	1.000			
(2) fsiz	0.363	1.000		
(3) prof	0.335	0.893	1.000	
(4) ownc	0.100	0.022	-0.042	1.000

Source: Author (2025)

In the case of the correlation between the independent and dependent variables of this study, the results obtain from the Spearman rank correlation above shows that there exist a positive association between firm size (0.363) and the dependent variable of carbon emission disclosure during the period under study. The table also shows that there exists a positive association between profitability (0.335) and the dependent variable of carbon emission disclosure during the period under study. Finally, the result shows that there also exists a positive association between ownership concentration (0.100) and the dependent variable of carbon emission disclosure during the period under study. All associations are seen to be weak and thus we cannot suspect the presence of multicollinearity among the explanatory variables.

4.3 Binary Logit Regression Analyses

Specifically, to examine the cause-effect relationships between the dependent variables and independent variables of the study, the study employ binary logit regression since the dependent variable is dichotomous. The result obtained is presented below.

Table 4.4: Binary Logistic Regression Result

	CAEM Model (Logistic Regression)	CAEM Model (Marginal Effect)
CONS.	-43.121 {0.005} **	
FSIZ	4.425 {0.000} ***	0.180 {0.000} ***
PROF	2.316 {0.019} **	0.094 {0.019} **
OWNC	0.032 {0.678}	0.001 {0.679}
LR(prob>chi2)	18.77 (0.0003) **	
Pseudo R- Squared	0.4182	
Goodness of Fit Test	38.92 {1.0000}	
VIF/Cond.Num	2.04/86.16(0.3881)	
Sensitivity	98.89%	
Specificity	33.33%	
Classification	94.79%	

Note: (1) bracket {} are p-values; (2) **, *, implies statistical significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively**

In the table above, it is observed from the Logistic regression of the carbon emission disclosure model that the Pseudo R-squared value of 0.4182 shows that about 42% of the systematic variations in carbon emission disclosure of the pooled oil and gas firms over the period of interest was jointly explained by the independent variables in the model. The unexplained part of carbon emission disclosure can be attributed to exclusion of other independent variables that can impact on carbon emission disclosure but were captured in the error term. The LR Statistics of the logistic regression [18.77 {0.0003}] shows that the model on the overall is statistically significant at 5% level, this means that the Logistic regression model is valid and can be used for statistical inference. Furthermore, the results of the LR Statistics are confirmed by the Pearson goodness of fit test [38.92 {1.0000}] indicating that the model on the overall is fit. From the foregoing, the study subjects the model into further diagnostic test to validate the reliability of the estimates.

Collinearity can mainly be detected with the help of tolerance and its reciprocal, called variance inflation factor (VIF). The tolerance is the percentage of the variance in a given predictor that cannot be explained by the other predictors. Tolerance close to 1 indicates that there is no collinearity, whereas a value close to zero suggests that collinearity may be a threat. There is no formal cut-off value to use with tolerance for determining presence of collinearity (Midi, Sarkar,

& Rana, 2013). Myers (1990) suggests a tolerance value below 0.1 indicates serious collinearity problem and Menard (2011) suggests that a tolerance value less than 0.2 indicates a potential collinearity problem. As a rule of thumb, a tolerance of 0.1 or less is a cause for concern. Moreover, eigen values for the condition indices and the variance proportions for each explanatory variable is used to identify collinearity. If any eigen value is larger than others, then the regression parameters can be greatly affected by small changes in the explanatory variables or outcome. If the eigen values are fairly similar then the fitted model is likely to be unchanged by small changes in the measured variables (Rana, Midi, & Sarkar, 2010). When there is no collinearity at all, the eigen values and condition indices will equal unity. As collinearity increases, eigen values will be both greater and smaller than unity. If one or more of the eigenvalues are small (close to zero) and the corresponding condition number is large, then we have an indication of multicollinearity. There is no hard and fast rule about how much larger a condition index needs to be indicated collinearity problems. Specifically, as indicated in the table above, a mean VIF value of 2.04 shows that VIF is within the benchmark value of 10, this indicates the absence of multicollinearity, and this means no independent variable should be dropped from the model.

Sensitivity (also called the true positive rate) measures the proportion of actual positives which are correctly identified as such and is complementary to the false negative rate while Specificity (also called the true negative rate) measures the proportion of negatives which are correctly identified as such and is complementary to the false positive rate. Particularly, the classification table shows that out of 93 cases that fell into the group of carbon emission disclosure samples, 89 cases were predicted correctly with 98.89% sensitivity accuracy while 2 of 3 cases that fell into the group of those that did not disclose carbon emission samples were predicted correctly and with 33.33% specificity accuracy. However, the study finds that the overall accuracy rate is seen to be roughly 94.79% which suggests that the model is free from any significant bias hence can be employed for interpretation and policy recommendation.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The findings from this study shows that the independent variable of firm size is a positive and significant determinant of carbon emission disclosure among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The result implies that a 1% increase in firm size will significantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 18% during the period under study. Resources owned by the firm can be reflected in its size. The larger the size of the firm, the higher its resources (Choi, Lee, & Psaros, 2013). The size of the firm is measured by the size of the firm's assets. The size of the firm is one factor that investors consider for investing. Large firms tend to provide detailed information to meet the information needs of their users, such as investors, management, government, and other information users. Stakeholder involvement in decisions regarding environmental, health, and safety (EHS) issues develops due to a decrease in public trust and the desire of stakeholders to participate more. This raises expectations of transparency and accountability, or interest in demonstrating responsiveness to public concerns. Legitimacy theory state that companies have responsibility to their stakeholder. Due to this theory, large firms should disclose all relevant information to their stakeholders as a corporate responsibility and accountability. Large companies are considered to have more resources to cover pollution reduction costs and related costs (Freedman and Jaggi, 2005). This is in line with the study by Kalu

et al. (2016) suggested the hypothesis that large firms have more resources to cover the cost of pollution reduction. Therefore, the assumption is that large companies will reveal more information than smaller companies. The availability of resources is critical to addressing issues related to climate change mitigation, which often require the company to operate significantly. All research on greenhouse gas emission disclosure found significant positive correlations between company size and information disclosure (Rankin et al., 2011); (Berthelot and Robert, 2011).

Furthermore, the result shows that the independent variable of profitability as measured in terms of return on asset is a positive and significant determinant of carbon emission disclosure among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The result implies that a 1% increase in profitability will significantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 9% during the period under study. The study by Kalu et al. (2016) suggested that the advantages of giving companies a pool of resources for environmental mitigation and reporting activities. In addition, carbon disclosure acts as a means to achieve public trust and legitimacy. This disclosure could be a means of achieving public trust and legitimacy in terms of how profits are made, not on environmental costs. The empirical evidence of how greenhouse gas disclosure affects profitability is mixed. According to Brammer and Pavelin (2006) it should be noted that profitability allows managers to gather resources that can be used to absorb environmental reporting costs. Studies argue that profitable companies are more vulnerable to the public, so interested parties may be interested in how companies generate profits (Berthelot and Robert, 2011); (Chithambo, 2013). Thus, profitable companies facing public pressure on how they make profits, can use information disclosure. Such disclosure of environmental information justifies their benefits (Bewley and Li, 2000). Prado-Lorenzo et al. (2009) found evidence of a significant negative correlation between profitability and disclosure with respect to GHG size of profitability, but no significant relationship with the second profitability indicator. A study conducted by Freedman and Jaggi (2005) reported a non-significant relationship with profitability. However, other studies have found significant positive correlations (Berthelot and Robert, 2011). The idea seems to be consistent with the profitability from voluntary disclosure as a means of transmitting information to outside investors viewed as a tool to gain a competitive advantage. The idea of this theory is that companies can use voluntary environmental disclosures to signal that their intangible assets will help ensure future income.

Finally, the result shows that the independent variable of ownership concentration is a positive and insignificant determinant of carbon emission disclosure among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The result implies that a 1% increase in ownership concentration will insignificantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 1% during the period under study. Institutional ownership has an important role in monitoring management because with the existence of institutional ownership, it will encourage more optimal supervision. Widyaningsih *et al.* (2017) stated that monitoring will surely ensure prosperity for shareholders. The influence of institutional ownership as regulatory agents is suppressed through their considerable investment in the capital market so as to impede opportunistic manager behavior. Greater institutional ownership will improve monitoring of the company, thus revealing all the activities undertaken by the company will improve the positive image to the stakeholders. The disclosure of the environment will increase the value of the company and assist in the company's ongoing development. Ho and Tower (2011) indicate that the concentration of ownership indicated

a consistent positive correlation with voluntary disclosure. Companies with greater foreign and institutional ownership have significant and positive correlation with the level of voluntary disclosure. Similar results were also found by Cotter and Najah (2012), institutional investors positively affected with climate changes disclosure. Results of the research by Borghei-Ghomi and Leung (2013) discovered that institutional ownership has positive effect on carbon emission disclosure. A company that has considerably high institutional ownership will be under pressure of the stakeholders or shareholders. Hence, relevant to the disclosure, the company will voluntarily disclose additional reports that are consistent with stakeholder theory.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Disclosure of carbon emission is usually reported in annual reports and / or sustainability reports. Theories that explain the disclosure of carbon emission in this study are legitimacy theory, stakeholder theory, and agency theory. Legitimacy theory describes companies and societies having social contracts in which companies have a demand to align corporate activities with values and norms prevailing in the community so that the companies get the legitimacy (recognition) from the community. Stakeholder theory explains that the company in running the company not only to seek profit but also provide benefits to stakeholders. Agency theory explains that there is information asymmetry between agents (Management) and principals (shareholders). Companies with superior environmental performance have a proactive environmental strategy. The theory of legitimacy explains that the company has a social contract with the community. The company is expected to perform its activities in accordance with the values and norms prevailing in the community so that the company gets recognition from the public. This can be obtained by aligning the company's activities with the values and norms of society, such as by preserving the surrounding environment. The better the environmental performance the higher the company is to gain legitimacy from the community.

Overall, the empirical findings of this study are mixed in proving the criteria influencing the disclosure of carbon emission reporting by drawing samples from listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that a 1% increase in firm size will significantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 18% during the period under study. Furthermore, the study concludes that a 1% increase in profitability will significantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 9% during the period under study. The result implies that a 1% increase in ownership concentration will insignificantly increase the disclosure of carbon emission among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria by about 1% during the period under study. In general, this study recommends that large firms should try to report more on carbon emission to bridge information asymmetry and increase stakeholders' confidence. Furthermore, there is a tendency to maintain the informative asymmetry and correspondingly potentially higher conflicts of interest, to the detriment of other stakeholders, particularly minority shareholders, assuming a strict link between the majority shareholders and the board of directors. Just like most previous related studies, this research will not be complete without providing few suggestions for other scholars who may wish to do similar research work. Some aspects of this study are yet to be concluded, such as establishing co-integration among other variables in the time of structural changes or breaks. Furthermore, similar studies should be carried out by incorporating non-finance sector.

REFERENCES

- Adediran, S. A., & Alade, S. O. (2016). The impact of environmental accounting on corporate performance in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(23), 141-152.
- Agustia, D., Sawarjuwono, T., & Dianawati, W. (2019). The mediating effect of environmental management accounting on green innovation-Firm value relationship. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 9(2), 299-306.
- Ahmad, A. (2012). Environmental Accounting and Reporting Practices: Significance and Issues: Bewley, K., & Li, Y. (2000). Disclosure of environmental information by Canadian manufacturing companies: A voluntary disclosure perspective. *Advances in Environmental Accounting and Management*, 1, 26-45.
- Amedu, J.M., Iliemena, R.O. & Umaigba, F.T. (2019). Value relevance of sustainability reporting in Nigerian manufacturing companies. *Journal of Global Accounting*, 6(2), 131 – 147. www.researchgate.net
- Andon, P., Baxter, J. and Chua, W.F. (2015), “Accounting for stakeholders and making accounting useful”, *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 52 No. 7, pp. 986-1002.
- Barbera, M., & Coyte, R. (1999). *Shareholder Value Demystified: an explanation of methodologies and use*. UNSW Press.
- Bebbington, J., & Gray, R. (2001). An account of sustainability: failure, success and a reconceptualization. *Critical perspectives on accounting*, 12(5), 557-587.
- Bennett, M., & James, P. (1998). ISO 14031 and the future of environmental performance evaluation. *Greener Management International*, 71-71.
- Beredugo, S. B. & Mefor, I. P., (2012). The Impact of Environmental Accounting and Reporting on Sustainable Development in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 3 (7), 55-87.
- Boyd, J. (1998). *The benefits of improved environmental accounting: An economic framework to identify priorities* (No. 1318-2016-103115).
- Brealey, R. M., & Myers, S. (1991). SC (1996), Principles of Corporate Finance. *McGraw-Hill, cap, 14*, 17-18.
- Brouwers, R., Schoubben, F., Van Hulle, C., & Van Uytbergen, S. (2014). The link between corporate environmental performance and corporate value: A literature review. *Review of Business and Economic Literature*, 58(4), 343-374.
- Cao, Y., Liu, J., Yu, Y., & Wei, G. (2017). Impact of environmental regulation on green growth in China’s manufacturing industry—based on the Malmquist-Luenberger index and the

- system GMM model. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27(33), 41928-41945.
- Chong, Z., Qin, C., & Ye, X. (2017). Environmental regulation and industrial structure change in china: Integrating spatial and social network analysis. *Sustainability*, 9(8), 1465.
- Clarkson, P. M., Fang, X., Li, Y., & Richardson, G. (2013). The relevance of environmental disclosures: Are
- Cheng, B., Ioannou, I., & Serafeim, G. (2014). Corporate social responsibility and access to finance. *Strategic management journal*, 35(1), 1-23.
- Cho, C. H., & Patten, D. M. (2013). Green accounting: Reflections from a CSR and environmental disclosure perspective. *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 24(6), 443-447.
- De Beer, P., & Friend, F. (2006). Environmental accounting: A management tool for enhancing corporate environmental and economic performance. *Ecological Economics*, 58(3), 548-560.
- Deegan, C. (2002). Introduction: The legitimising effect of social and environmental disclosures—a theoretical foundation. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*.
- Dechezleprêtre, A., & Sato, M. (2020). The impacts of environmental regulations on competitiveness. *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*.
- Dhaliwal, D., Li, O. Z., Tsang, A., & Yang, Y. G. (2014). Corporate social responsibility disclosure and the cost of equity capital: The roles of stakeholder orientation and financial transparency. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 33(4), 328-355.
- Ditz, D. W., Ranganathan, J., & Banks, R. D. (1995). *Green ledgers: case studies in corporate environmental accounting*. World Resources Institute.
- Dunk, A. S. (2002). Product quality, environmental accounting and quality performance. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*.
- Egbunike, A. P., & Okoro, G. E. (2018). Does green accounting matter to the profitability of firms? A canonical assessment. *Ekonomski horizonti*, 20(1), 17-26.
- Emeka-Nwokeji, N., & Osisoma, B. C. (2019). Sustainability disclosures and market value of firms in emerging economy: Evidence from Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 7(3), 1-19.
- Emeka-Nwokeji, N. A., & Okeke, P. C. (2019). Evaluating Corporate Environmental Disclosures and Performance of Quoted Non-Financial Firms in Nigeria. *Journal of accounting, business, and social sciences*, 1(2), 119-132.

- Emmanuel, U. (2021). Environmental accounting disclosure and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and International Business Management*, 9(2), 71-81.
- Everett, J., & Neu, D. (2000, March). Ecological modernization and the limits of environmental accounting?. In *Accounting Forum* (Vol. 24, No. 1, pp. 5-29). Taylor & Francis.
- Gray, R., & Bebbington, J. (2000). Environmental accounting, managerialism and sustainability: Is the planet safe in the hands of business and accounting?. In *Advances in environmental accounting & management*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Gray, R., Owen, D., & Adams, C. (1996). *Accounting & accountability: changes and challenges in corporate social and environmental reporting*. Prentice Hall.
- Gray, R., Owen, D., & Adams, C. (1996). *Accounting & accountability: changes and challenges in corporate social and environmental reporting*. Prentice Hall.
- Griffin, P. A., & Sun, Y. (2011). Going green: Market reaction to CSRwire news releases. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 32(2), 93-113.
- Ironkwe, U. I., & Success, G. O. (2017). Environmental accounting and sustainable development: A study of Niger Delta Area of Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 6(5), 1-12.
- Jasch, C. (2003). The use of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) for identifying environmental costs. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 11(6), 667-676.
- Jariya, A. I. (2015). Environmental disclosures in annual reports of Sri Lankan corporate: a content analysis. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 6(8), 350-357.
- Jensen, M. (2001). Value maximisation, stakeholder theory, and the corporate objective function. *European financial management*, 7(3), 297-317.
- Khajavi, S., & Zare, A. (2016). The effect of audit quality on stock crash risk in Tehran Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 6(1).
- Kim, J. B., Song, B. Y., & Zhang, Y. (2015). Earnings performance of major customers and bank loan contracting with suppliers. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 59, 384-398.
- Laska Najul and Maji S. G. (2018) performance in Asimorea. In *Asian Review of Accounting*. 26 (4), 414-443. doi: 10.1108/ARA-02-2017-0029.

- Lusiana, M., Haat, M. H. C., Saputra, J., Yusliza, M. Y., Muhammad, Z., & Bon, A. T. A Review of Green Accounting, Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure, Financial Performance and Firm Value Literature.
- Makori, D. M., & Jagongo, A. (2013). Environmental accounting and firm profitability: An empirical analysis of selected firms listed in Bombay Stock Exchange, India. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(18), 248-256.
- Makori, D. M., & Jagongo, A. (2013). Working capital management and firm profitability: Empirical evidence from manufacturing and construction firms listed on Nairobi securities exchange, Kenya. *International journal of accounting and taxation*, 1(1), 1-14.
- Masud, M. M., Azam, M. N., Mohiuddin, M., Banna, H., Akhtar, R., Alam, A. F., & Begum, H. (2017). Adaptation barriers and strategies towards climate change: Challenges in the agricultural sector. *Journal of cleaner production*, 156, 698-706.
- Makori, D. M., & Jagongo, A. (2013). Environmental accounting and firm profitability: An empirical analysis of selected firms listed in Bombay stock exchange, India. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(18), 248-256.
- Matsumura, E. M., Prakash, R., & Vera-Munoz, S. C. (2014). Firm-value effects of carbon emissions and carbon disclosures. *The accounting review*, 89(2), 695-724.
- Mistry, V., Sharma, U., & Low, M. (2014). Management accountants' perception of their role in accounting for sustainable development: An exploratory study. *Pacific Accounting Review*.
- Nakajima, M., Kimura, A., & Wagner, B. (2015). Introduction of material flow cost accounting (MFCA) to the supply chain: a questionnaire study on the challenges of constructing a low-carbon supply chain to promote resource efficiency. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 108, 1302-1309.
- Ogoun, S., & Ekpulu, G. A. (2020). Environmental Reporting and Operational Performance: A Study of Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 6(1).
- Okegbe, T. O., Paulinus, E. C., & Onyebuchi, O. H. (2019). Environmental Management Reporting and Corporate Performance: Evidence from Natural Resources, Agriculture, Oil and Gas Firms in Nigeria. *Environmental Management*, 3(5).
- Onyali, I.C., Okafor, T.G., & Egolum, P. (2014). An Assessment of Environmental Information Reporting on organizational performance of selected oil and gas companies in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

- Osemene, O.F., Kasum, A.S. & Yahaya, K.A. (2012). Environmental Audit Practices in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigeria. *Annals of Management Sciences. International Centre for Business and Management Excellence*, 1(1), 10-40.
- Oyedokun, G. E., Egberioyinemi, E., & Tonademukaila, A. (2019). Environmental Accounting Disclosure and Firm Value of Industrial Goods Companies in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance (IOSR-JEF)*, 10(1), 7-27.
- Research Journal of Finance and Accounting, 4(3), 57-73. Financial Ratios for Accounting Research
- Citation DataSSRN, ISSN: 1556-5068 Publication Year 2017 Retrieved from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1478138
- Saidi, K., & Hammami, S. (2015). The impact of CO2 emissions and economic growth on energy consumption in 58 countries. *Energy Reports*, 1, 62-70.
- Sarah Yuliarini, Zaleha Othman Othman, Ku Nor Izah Ismaila. Environmental accounting practices: A regulatory and internal management perspective. *Journal of Economic & Financial Studies* 5 (3), 01-11, 2017
- Schaltegger S, Burritt R, Petersen H. An introduction to corporate environmental management: Striving for Sustainability. *Greenleaf Publishing*: UK; 2003
- Schaltegger, S., & Burritt, R. L. (2006). Corporate sustainability accounting: a nightmare or a dream coming true?. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 15(5), 293-295.
- Shil, N. C. (2009). Micro finance for poverty alleviation: A commercialized view. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 1(2), 191-205.
- Wahyuni, W., Meutia, I., & Syamsurijal, S. (2019). The Effect of Green Accounting Implementation on Improving the Environmental Performance of Mining and Energy Companies in Indonesia. *Binus Business Review*, 10(2), 131-137.
- Yakhou, M & Dorweiler, V (2004). Environmental Accounting: An Essential Component of Business Strategy. USA: *John Wiley and Sons Ltd*.